

SUBJECT AND LANGUAGE COLLABORATED LEARNING AS AN INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHOD IN ESP

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***Annotation.** The article is devoted to the consideration of the idea of subject and language collaborated learning in the system of higher professional education and analysis of new concepts and approaches to professionally oriented training developed in methodological science, with taking into consideration their influence on students' motivation to learn a foreign language. Activation of educational activities has always been one of the primary tasks of education in general and, in particular, teaching foreign languages to students of non-linguistic specialties. This determines relevance of this work.*

***Key words:** collaboration, non-linguistic, professional, communication, integration, content.*

Today, a university graduate must not only have good knowledge in his field, but also be fluent in a foreign language and be able to read and translate professional texts, and also use a foreign language for communication. Thus, a professionally oriented approach to teaching foreign languages in non-linguistic universities is of particular relevance. The goal of training should be to achieve a sufficient level for the practical use of a foreign language in future professional activities. It is important not only to master communication skills in a foreign language, but also to acquire special knowledge in the specialty. Unfortunately, at the present stage, teaching a foreign language in universities, taking into account the professional orientation of students, still does not meet the proper level. Therefore, in order to teach students a foreign language necessary for their future professional activities, it is necessary to

rethink their goals and content. A modern professionally oriented approach to teaching a foreign language should develop in students the ability to communicate in a foreign language in specific professional, business, scientific fields and situations, taking into account the characteristics of professional thinking for organizing motivational, practical and research activities. This is its main difference from language teaching for general educational purposes. The essence of professionally oriented foreign language teaching lies, first of all, in its integration with special disciplines in order to obtain additional professional knowledge and skills, and the formation of professionally significant personality qualities. And here the teacher may encounter certain difficulties, since due to linguistic or pedagogical education he does not know special terminology, and, therefore, he additionally needs to study the basics of a particular specialty, basic and professional vocabulary. And this is where the collaboration and joint activities of two subject teachers should take place. To achieve this goal, in foreign language classes you can use materials, the selection of which is carried out relying on the subject teacher. It provides information and materials related to the basic concepts of the future specialty, as well as create situations in which students could use the acquired theoretical knowledge to solve practical problems. Also important is the help of a subject teacher, a specialist in a particular field, to connect the latter to team work with students in the learning

process. In addition, a linguist teacher must be prepared for the fact that students can correct the mistakes of a teacher who does not have the specifics of their future non-linguistic specialty. It is also impossible for students to master professional communication skills without selecting authentic texts, creating specific teaching strategies and skills in various professional areas; a subject teacher, a specialist in a particular field, will help the linguist-teacher with it. Thus, the content of teaching a foreign language should include:

- a number of communicative tasks, situations and materials, taking into account the future professional field of activity of students;
- relevant linguistic material;
- development of professional skills that affect the level of practical knowledge of foreign languages, including communication in real situations;
- certain professional vocabulary, special terminology in a foreign language;
- work with special dictionaries, glossaries and reference books in the specialty.

Consequently, a professionally oriented approach to learning a foreign language when preparing students of non-linguistic specialties should be a didactic system and have a scientific basis for determining learning goals, selecting and structuring its content, choosing forms, methods and means of teaching. This approach helps future specialists obtain the necessary knowledge of a foreign language in conjunction with the development of their professional skills and abilities. As a result, graduates must be ready for speech professional interaction (to master different types of speech activity based on professionally oriented vocabulary), as well as for independent activity in the conditions of foreign language professional communication. Therefore, the collaboration of two subject specialists: a linguist teacher and a subject specialist in professional specialization is an active area of research in TEFL. However, exploring the process of collaborative planning and collaborative learning, and ways of collaborating between language-teachers and the content-teachers that can be implemented is given less attention than it should be. Different current research works show that ESP teachers need to become more aware of the collaborative process, not only for course design and instructional materials preparation, but also for their productivity and professional development. Collaboration is attracting significant interest and anticipation around the world, and many studies highlight the importance of ensuring that teachers are equipped to meet the demands of this area. ESP has been introduced into higher education in many countries and is taught in all fields. However, differences in qualifications and teaching methods, as well as limited specialist knowledge of teachers, represent serious problems affecting the ESP situation. The fact that the vast majority of ESP teachers in universities have been trained to teach general English is a real problem and affects the quality of teaching.

Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998) identified some specific roles for the perception practitioner as a teacher: course designer and material provider, collaborator, researcher and evaluator. These specific roles make the ESP practitioner less like a general English teacher. In the absence or limited specialized knowledge, the ESP teacher's job, in this case, can be extremely specific, so that he can provide the necessary knowledge in a particular area. Due to the fact that in teaching ESP teachers face challenges related to the content of disciplines that are so different in their background knowledge and experience. “Teamwork can bridge the gap between science and language.” (Hansen & Hamman, 1980, cited in Almagro & Martos, 2002, p. 10). In other words, ESP teacher collaboration with content teachers is seen as a critical way

to promote professional development and enhance classroom effectiveness. Dudley Evan and St. John (1998) refer to collaboration “as integration between specialized activities and language.” ESP practitioners as collaborators explore deeper knowledge of subject content in the language. Collaborative or team learning can be implemented differently in many contexts. Buckley (2000:4) states that “team learning involves a group of instructors working purposefully, regularly, and collaboratively to help a group of students learn.” ESP teachers and content teachers work together, sharing knowledge and experience to plan course content and teaching ESP strategies that will address students' learning needs, prepare learning materials and assessment tools for a group of students. The purpose of this article is to talk about the features of cooperation, training between ESP teachers and teachers of the definite field and the impact of this cooperation on ESP teacher development. It aims to find answers to the following research questions:

- A) How ESP teachers perceive collaboration with subject teachers?
- b) What are the difficulties and problems which ESP teachers face when working in collaboration with content teachers?
- c) What is the impact of cooperation on teacher development and ESP teaching situations?

Collaboration is defined as “a process where interested parties can come together for a common purpose, that is, exchange information, listen to each other's experiences, and potentially work together to achieve a Common Goal.” (Mazur and Doran, 2010, p.146) The participation of each person in this process is important for its achievement. Gode Mann (cited in Howlett , 2011) stated that collaboration should not only be interdisciplinary, but should also be based on a transdisciplinary approach. In other words, collaboration involves not only the participants from different disciplines, but it requires participants to bring their expertise as part of the process to work to overcome their weaknesses and biases that they have developed as a result of their training and role.

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